

M5

TRL5 achieved- M16 Prototype components / breadboard validated in a simulated or representative environment verified by US Air Force Research Laboratory TRL calculator.

The minimum TRL of each technology as listed in the DoA Table 1.1 has been achieved. For the RoCSI eDNA sampler this has been exceeded (this is TRL7). The results of this analysis are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1 TechOceanS technologies TRL assessment M16

Technology	TechOceanS TRL transition activity (from DoA)	Notes on TRL progress	TRL assessment
eDNA sampler (RoCSI)	Transition to pressure-balanced system, uplift in number of samples, improved power consumption, interfacing, and rugged design	The pressure maintaining system has proved robust and of reasonable cost and is maintained. The alignment of injectors with cartridges has been developed to be more robust. The device has been tested in simulated (pressure pot) environment and has completed at sea missions	7
eDNA sampler (pressure balanced)	As above	A new pressure-balanced, lower cost and more compact concept has been developed. A benchtop prototype has been constructed and tested vs synthetic samples. Components have been tested in simulated environments (pressure pot)	5
Microplastics Sampler	An automated filter sampler (MAPS) will collect samples for later analysis (e.g. FTIR microscopy) in the micro to millimetre range	An adaptation of the pressure balanced sampler (above) has been evaluated for large volume (100 L) and microplastic samples. Options for throughput increase	5

		and microplastic contamination decrease have been developed.	
In situ nucleic acid sensor	Adaptation of existing filter sampling (above) and lysis systems, development of new extraction and purification system and/or robust assays with crude sample, adapted detection system for multiplexing	New molecular assays and techniques have been developed. Each element of the multistage assay has been prototyped. A new fluid format has been developed and this prototyped and tested in the laboratory. Components (reagent chambers) have been tested and performance verified in simulated environments	5
Imaging Workflow	Onboard data processing, acoustic/satellite data transmission, synthetically trained lightweight deep-learning feature extraction algorithms, image formation models for conversion of labelled imagery to sensor specific representations	A new 3D object scanning system and image library generation technique has been developed and image classification algorithms advanced. AI and data compression tools have been developed.	5
Imaging Hardware	Adaptation of existing hardware to support the above workflow giving BioCam and UVP6 remote awareness of benthic and pelagic image observations	low-bandwidth communication protocols and data compression hardware have been developed for BioCAM. New UVP6 interface specifications and lighting system have been adjusted and characterised through modelling and testing	5
Optical PhytoPP sensor (MicroSTAF)	Reduced size and power of time	A design with reduced size and power has	6

	resolved fluorometer for Primary Productivity	been developed and components tested. Existing designs (LabSTAF, AutoSTAF) have delivered data for science or in simulated tests.	
Bio-assay sensor	Development of robust bio-assays, new multiplexing and reagent storage schemes, integration with LOC platform	New bio-assays and sample handling systems have been developed. Both a Lab on a disc and new pressure balanced in situ microfluidic format have been developed with components tested in the laboratory and in simulated environments	5
Biogeochemical sensors	Reduced size, sampling time, power for smaller platforms	New concepts for improved valves, pumps and time optimised analysis have been developed and tested in the laboratory and simulated environments	6
Microcytometer	Integration of impedance spectroscopy, imaging and optical detection, integration with LOC platform	A new in situ design has been developed and optics and impedance detection proven in the laboratory with cultures and particles. A pressure tolerant design has been developed and components tested.	5

